

Supplementary Material 6 – Uncertainty Analysis

SM6) Clamping Mask geographically exhibiting the combined uncertainty level of final ensemble forecast model. For better visualization, we did not cropped the mapped result to the administrative extent of Brazil, providing the total modeled area to demonstrate that the concerning levels of inaccuracies are restricted to Chile, Bolivia, Peru and Argentina. In Brazil, in the northeast region, some areas of imprecision are distributed in islands, however with extremely low values, and which do not jeopardize the accuracy of our results for the analytical purposes.

